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RESEARCH ARTICLE

The Impact of Covid-19 on Farmers in Maharashtra

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This paper discusses issues regarding the effect of COVID-19 on the Small Farmers in Maharashtra. The economy falls down rapidly. This impacted on farmers heavily. The COVID-19 is running riot in the state's rural hinterland, where most agricultural activity takes place and more than 75% people depend upon the income generated from these activities. This pandemic impacted on Rabbi season as well as Kharif season crops. In Maharashtra Crops like Soyabeans, cottons, vegetable-fruits farming and those who are in diary business, horticulture have been hit badly. Farmers from Vidharbha & Marathwada region impacted from this pandemic & Kokan-Western Maharashtra suffers a lot because with this pandemic they also suffer from 2 cyclones i.e. "NISARGA" "TOKATAY". Due to COVID-19 most of the farmers from Maharashtra are suffering from the problem of poverty. So this paper focuses on how the problems faced by farmers can be resolved, how the agricultural production will increase, what are the schemes started for farmers also think for the future even as the pandemic continues to rage, we have to put safety nets.

Keywords: Covid-19, lockdown, agriculture, farmer, Maharashtra

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INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic is a global health crisis that is already having devastating impacts on the world economy. India suffers a lot with that state like Maharashtra where is Agricultural backbone of economy, but due to COVID-19 it is showing a negative growth rate.

The economic shock will likely be much more severe for Maharashtra for two reasons. First, pre-COVID-19, the economy was already slowing down, compounding existing problems of unemployment, low incomes, rural distress, malnutrition, and widespread inequality & weather conditions.

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OBJECTIVES

- To study the impact of Covid 19 on agriculture sector in Maharashtra.
- To understand problems faced by farmers.
- To view on What are the solutions to overcome the problems faced by farmers in Maharashtra

IMPACT OF COVID 19 ON MAHARASHTRA'S ECONOMY

COVID-19 is disrupting some activities in agriculture and supply chains. Preliminary reports show that the non-availability of migrant labor is interrupting some harvesting activities. There are disruptions in supply chains because of transportation problems and market closed due to lockdown. Prices have declined for Jawari, cotton, Soyabine, vegetables, and other crops, yet consumers are often paying more. Media reports show that the closure of Retail shops, consumer service industry during depressing milk sales. Meanwhile, poultry farmers have been badly hit due to misinformation, particularly on social media, that chicken are the carriers of COVID-19. Marathwada & Vidarbha suffered from lack of water and in covid though the inter city transport stopped this problem arises. Also the Green Path of Maharashtra that is "Konkan" suffers from 2 dangerous cyclones i.e. "NISARGA" "TOKATAY". Though the state government of Maharashtra announces the many schemes for farmers and financial fund but it not efficient.

Maharashtra's economy is to grow at (-)8% in 2020-21 compared to 5.0% of the previous fiscal, according to the Economic Survey presented in the Assembly on Financial Budget 2020-21.

The survey said the unemployment rate in January to March 2020 was 5.6% as compared to 5.2% in October to December 2019. A total of 26,586 offences were reported in the State by October 2020, in which women were victims, as compared to 35,501 in 2018 and 37,112 in 2019, the report said. During 2020-21 upto

September the total FDI inflows in the State was Rs 27,143 crore.

Western Maharashtra is food factory of Maharashtra but it suffers lot, Marathwada & Vidarbha's are not able take foodgrains like Jawari-Bajari as well as Soyabine due to covid 19, Rice & Fruits production from Konkan also affected

Though the majority of farmers in Maharashtra have small holdings are facing financial problems, mental problems and the suiciding rate is also increased. Epitome Journal survey stating that 2 farmers are suiciding in 1 hr. Childrens of farmers are also not able to take online education. Farmers are facing overburden of Loans. The "Savkarshahi" is till yet not destroyed which is exploiting the small farmers. The situation is dangerous.

It is very difficult task for government to handle this situation but there are some solutions

- There should be proper implementation of Govt Schemes like Mahatma Jyotirao Shetkari Loan Waiver scheme.
- Take strict action against exploitation of rights of farmer.
- Take step to Eradicate unequality between small farmers & rich farmers
- By following all guidelines of covid-19 all markets should be open where farmer can sell there production
- Frame the policies which can give financial as well as educational support to farmer & family.

CONCLUSION

Covid-19 is pandemic no one can tell when it will be end so everyone should get ready to live with this covid & overcome the situation. The agricultural sector trying to overcome from this crisis now the responsibility of government as well as every citizen of Maharashtra is to help the farmers, raise the fund for them, create the market places where they can sell the

product ,make proper changes in MSP Policy.If everyone is aware of their responsibilities, the situation will soon be under control.

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